

The Impact of Industrial Revolution to Marketing

by

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Abstract

Technological advancements, which have risen above simply being a development, affect generation procedures and day by day life of consumers by changing their habits and behaviors. Looking at the creation of innovation and day by day life of the 1950s with today, the progressions are evidently taken note along these lines, continuing in a parallel way with the progressions. Marketing activities have changed over to Marketing 4.0. Thus, in the light of writing, this examination deliberately expects to uncover the adjustments in showcasing exercises dependent on innovative advancements and to clarify the unmistakable highlights of each advertising stages. Henceforth, this examination directly off the bat the adjustments in showcase exercises are explored as far as Changes in the industry, markets, and consumers. It is comprehended that advertising exercises can be inspected in four phases to be specific; Marketing 1.0, Marketing 2.0, Marketing 3.0 and Marketing 4.0 The distinctions in all stages are clarified in detail. At last, the change in showcasing Blend components have been examined dependent on Technological advancements. Thus, the relationship between industrial and marketing has been addressed in a comprehensive Manner.

Keywords: industrial 1.0 to 4.0, marketing 1.0 to 4.0, marketing mix

Introduction:

The world changes each second, the technology becomes obsolete within a week, and new products appear more often than we can keep track of it. This rate of advancement in the cutting-edge world requires completion of past information. Marketing is not an exception. Not very far in the past, it was sufficient to recognize your item so as to get a greater number of clients than you can serve, just as promoting, was unsophisticated and cheap. A bit later, individuals engrossed their way of life, and promoting has advanced – at that period, not simply the item is sold to the shoppers, however, the things that it brought to their lives, increasingly inventive, and so forth..

A bit later, individuals engrossed their way of life, and promoting has advanced – at that period, not simply the item is sold to the shoppers, however, the things that it brought to their lives, increasingly inventive, and so forth. Presently it is the ideal opportunity for promoting of the third era, which is going by human qualities. Today not simply the item and not, in any case, its picture is sold to the buyers, however, the chance to carry on with an increasingly important life, settling on buys and settling on decisions for some organization.

As per Brady [2], innovation has empowered the advancement of relationship advertising, which improves the connection between the purchaser and consumers thought about to the traditional transactional marketing mix entailing the 4P's. Effective marketing systems are today focused on relationship advertising to hold and draw in shoppers by gathering buyer fulfillment.

Evaluations of Industrial:

Globalization has multiplied the assortment of the elective items in the market; subsequently the dimension of rivalry in the business sectors has expanded. Marketing strategy has become significant for organizations to facilitate and sustain competitive advantages (Kotler and Keller, 2006). The increase in number of products with deferent brands has not been the only alteration in the market. As the choice of products has increased customers have started to compare the products. Especially the developments in information technologies have facilitated to gather information about products for consumers. Thus, consumers have become more conscious. Against the background briefly presented above, the point of this investigation is to decide the effects of industrial development on marketing activities. For this purpose, in the light of current literature, marketing activities are examined in four stages respectively; Marketing 1.0, Marketing 2.0, Marketing 3.0 and Marketing 4.0. The primary highlights of each marketing stages and the distinctions among them are inspected. Finally, the impacts of innovative developments on marketing mix elements are studied. Since this paper clarifies the connection among innovation and advertising exhaustively and comprehensively, it is believed that it makes a significant contribution not only to the body of knowledge but also to the practitioners to help them to understand the issue from a wider angle.

For quite a long time, products including food, clothing, houses, and weaponry were made by hand or with the assistance of work creatures. By the start of the nineteenth century, however, producing started to change significantly with the presentation of Industry 1.0, and operations quickly created from that point. Here is an outline of that development.

Industry 1.0:

The late of eighteenth century acquainted mechanical creation offices with the world. Water and steam-controlled machines were created to help laborers in the large-scale manufacturing of products. The principal weaving loom was presented in 1784. With the expansion underway effectiveness and scale, independent companies developed from serving a predetermined number of clients to huge associations with proprietors, supervisor and employees representatives serving a bigger number. Industry 1.0 can likewise be esteemed as the start of the business culture which concentrated similarly on quality, proficiency, and scale.

Industry 2.0:

By the start of the twentieth century, began the second modern insurgency – Industry 2.0. The principle supporter of this upset was the improvement of machines running power turned into the essential wellspring of intensity. It was simpler to use than water and steam and empowered organizations to focus control sources to singular machines. Inevitably machines were planned with their own capacity sources, making them increasingly convenient. This period in like manner watched the improvement of different organization programs that made it possible to extend the profitability and sufficiency of collecting workplaces. Division of work, where every specialist

completes a piece of the all-out activity, expanded profitability. Large scale manufacturing of products utilizing sequential construction systems ended up typical. American mechanical master Frederick Taylor familiar strategies of looking at work with the advance laborer and work environment techniques. Ultimately, in the nick of time and lean assembling standards further refined the manner by which fabricating organizations could improve their quality and yield.

Industry 3.0:

Over the most recent couple of many years of the twentieth century, the innovation and production of electronic contraptions, for instance, the transistor and, later, coordinated circuit chips, influenced it conceivable to additional to completely computerize singular machines to enhance or supplant administrators. This period also created the headway of programming structures to profit by the electronic gear. Coordinated frameworks, for example, material prerequisites arranging, were supplanted by big business assets arranging apparatuses that empowered individuals to plan, date-book and track thing courses through the creation line. Strain to lessen costs made numerous producers move segment and get together tasks to minimal effort nations. The all-inclusive geographic scattering brought about the formalization of the idea of store network the executives.

Industry 4.0:

In the 21st century, Industry 4.0 interfaces the web of things (IOT) with assembling procedures to enable structures to share information, separate it and use it to oversee clever exercises. It likewise joins front line advances including added substance fabricating, apply autonomy, man-made consciousness and other subjective advance simplify materials, and extended reality, as demonstrated by the article —Industry 4.0 and Manufacturing Ecosystems| by Deloitte University Press. The advancement of new innovation has been an essential driver of the development to Industry 4.0. A part of the activities at first made in the midst of the later periods of the twentieth century, for instance, manufacturing execution systems, shop floor control and item life cycle the board, were farsighted ideas that come up short on the innovation expected to make their total usage conceivable. Presently, Industry 4.0 can empower these undertakings to accomplish their most extreme limit.

Marketing evolution:

Many radical changes have taken place in the world since the Industrial Revolution. Especially rapid developments of information technologies increased the pace of the changes in the last decade. Nowadays the world has become a global place where both geographic and cultural boundaries between nations have become transparent and people all over the world have connected each other via social media and the internet. Technology and globalization have also changed the rules of trade. In business life, the data has become the most important asset of the companies and the companies which manage data properly have possessed the key to achievement. Keeping pace with the changes is required for sustaining the business life. Thus, marketing activities have transformed from Marketing 1.0 to Marketing 4.0 in a parallel way with technological developments.

Marketing 1.0:

Marketing 1.0 was the first stage of marketing which has consisted of various concepts namely production concepts, product concepts, selling concepts and marketing concepts. It is critical that modern upheaval had actuated to rise of Marketing 1.0 (Jara, 2012). Therefore; Marketing 1.0 began with generation ideas because of the Industrial insurgency. In the early days of Marketing 1.0, there were a small number of businesses engaging in production in the market and these businesses focused on achieving high production efficiency with low cost (Kotler and Keller, 2006, p. 15).

In order to ensure this, businesses used industrial machines and so that they could manufacture standardized products massively. In that term, consumers were regarded as passive and they had no impact on the production process of businesses (Nowacki, 2015).

In this stage, shoppers were as yet latent however organizations understood the essentialness of buyers leastways after a while; businesses noticed that quality and innovativeness were not sufficient for selling the products. Consequently, the selling concept came into the prominent topic.

Marketing 2.0:

Rapid progression in technology, globalization and economy led to change social and business life radically. On the one hand, the buyer power has increased in connection with economic conditions and the choice of goods in the market that customers could purchase have continued to increment with globalization, then again, correspondence and access to data have turned out to be simpler gratitude to innovative advancements. Especially Web 2.0 technologies altered the communication from monologs to dialogs (Tarabasz, 2013). These developments have begun a chain of particular changes in marketing.

As a result of these adjustments in showcasing, organizations revamped customary promoting blend components as 4C with the point of maintainable advertising (Kumar, et al. 2012). 4C was an abbreviation that comprised of the quicker of client arrangement, client cost, correspondence and comfort. It was thought that 4P reacted vender point of view, whereas 4C that reflected customer point of view (Mucuk, 2010, p. 33). Becoming a customer- arranged association required to think like clients and to give clients different advantages so organizations started to consider discovering an answer for client needs with their items to determine the real cost of product possession for consumers, to communicate with customers efficiently and to make products available in convenient place. Therefore, Marketing 2.0 focused on 4C in contrast to Marketing 1.0.

Marketing 3.0:

Marketing 3.0 is known as value-driven marketing applications (Kotler et al., 2010, p. 4). The center of interest shifted toward human as a whole in Marketing 3.0 (Varey, and McKie, 2010). In Marketing 1.0 businesses focused on merely functional benefits and these benefits were regarded as sufficient to satisfy the mind of customers.

In Marketing 2.0 besides functional benefits, businesses strived to promote their products with emotional benefits in order to enter into the heart of consumers. Because Marketing 3.0

treated the consumer as a human being who has mind, heart, and spirit, a new benefit as the spiritual benefit was added in Marketing 3.0.

Businesses should create value incentive so as to interest the spirit of purchasers. The natural and social variables rose because of extreme industrialization and globalization Sensitized clients regarding social issues The nature of social media encourages customers for sharing their experience so online networking impacts buy choice (Wang, et al., 2012). Additionally, social media accelerated viral content of businesses to reach many people p. Social media users share interesting viral content with their friends thus; viral content is displayed by a large gathering of individuals. Therefore, consumers engaged in an advertising campaign of businesses in marketing 3.0. friends.

Marketing 4.0:

Marketing 4.0 risen in outcome of different changes sourced from extreme worldwide challenge, another kind of purchasers and quick advancement in innovations (Vassileva, 2017). Actually, whether it is a new phenomenon or it is a modification of existing marketing implementations is discussed in the literature (Jara et al., 2012, p. 854; Tarabasz, 2013, p. 129; Nowacki 2015, p. 315). Like previous marketing concepts, customers are still the center of the marketing activities, however; the difference lies behind the market conditions.

Marketing 4.0 is operated in extremely cybernetic marketing system in which business transactions and customer activities can be monitored in real time(Dholakia, et al., 2010).

Marketing 4.0 focuses on the satisfaction of customers' needs and desires like the first two generations and it tries to create value for all entities like the third generation. In addition to them, it offers a direct interaction of consumers with products with enhanced technology (Jara et al., 2012, p. 854; Vassileva, 2017, p. 47).Traditional trade firstly changed over into e-trade and after that m-exchange. Innovation improves constantly and influences both business and public activity. For this reason, the main purpose of Marketing 4.0 is to predict future developments in the market and mold marketing activities based on this foresight. Therefore, consumer insights, data management, and advanced analytics are key factors of Marketing 4.0 in order to forecast future trends (Vassileva, 2017, p. 49).

The effects of technological developments on marketing mix:

The marketer of a company carries out his marketing tasks by providing a market offer. This offer comprises four elements namely product, price, place, and promotion. These four elements together constitute the marketing mix. Technological innovative advancements are immensely impacting the fortunes of the businesses. In business, technology is not only leading to many innovative products but also production, pricing of products, information processing, communication and logistics and all of them have been revolutionized by technology advancement.

The developments in technology enable marketing activities to develop, Simplify and accelerate with the use of new tools and new techniques (Jayaram, et al., 2015). In the latest form of marketing, one of the most valuable assets of the businesses is the capability of adaptation to technological improvements. Therefore, businesses reshaped their Marketing mix elements namely product, price, place and promotion strategies based on the present technology.

Product:

It is seen that improvements in innovation cause distinctive changes in physical items and administrations. In the first-place physical items, the salient changes in physical products can be listed as product Standardization with mass production, product shelf life extension, product diversification, personalized products, and smarter products.

As industries have developed with technologies, the capacity and the speed of production have increased with the use of assembly line technologies in manufacturing so that businesses started to mass production (Adetayo, et al., 1999). As a product- based methodology, Marketing 1.0 concentrated on creation in extensive sums. Regardless of the craving of buyers, businesses aimed to maximize their profits by diminishing cost of manufacture with standardized products.

As competition has increased and manufacturing technologies have improved, businesses tried to differentiate themselves with high-quality products. Hence, the key advertising idea of Marketing 1.0 was item improvement. Information technologies caused the emergence of Marketing 2.0 applications. Internet provided consumers easy access to product information and a wide variety of product choice. Consumers turned out to be progressively cognizant and requested customized items that precisely met their specific needs and wants (Rust, and Espinoza, 2006).It is seen that technological products such as mobile phone and laptops become smaller, lighter and smarter in Marketing 3.0. Then again, environmental sensitivity is another significant feature of the products in Marketing 3.0. Products Such as household appliances are designed in order to consume less energy and water In Marketing 4.0, human-machine connection increases. Therefore, businesses produce and packages products so as to energize this intelligence. Businesses start to use barcodes And QR codes on the package of the products and advertising messages so that consumers can access all information by scanning these codes.

Price:

Technological developments play a significant job in deciding the pricing strategies of products. Developments in globalization and information technologies have transformed countries Into open markets (Albay, 2010).The ability of businesses to access resources all over the world has provided a significant cost advantage to businesses.

In addition to providing cost savings and competitive advantage, modern present-day innovations have additionally diminished the expense of getting to data and joining worldwide markets (Acs, and Preston, 1997), selling on the web gives explicit favorable circumstances to organizations, for example, utilizing fewer employees, reducing the cost of setting up the retail facade and disposing of delegates.

Besides, web-based business exchanges are burdened at lower rates, or expenses are not demanded on internet business exchanges in certain nations, for example, the United Kingdom, The difference in the cost elements of the businesses in the electronic environment can also be reflected in the prices of the products and therefore, it is seen that the prices in the electronic environment are lower than the prices in the physical environment.

Place:

The most critical part of the effect of mechanical advancements in dissemination channels on organizations is that the developments in data and correspondence innovations empower the conveyance channel the board to be done all the more effectively (Waters, 2003). The Internet,

and extranet, which provide communication between distribution channel members, ensure more open, more frequent and timely communication among channel members (Kolchak, 1997, p. 231). The increase in communication encourages and quickens the offer of data in organizations with the goal that it improves the capacity of diverting individuals to work in coordination. Efficient communication among channel members ensures efficient inventory management as well (Tekin, and Zerenler, 2005). In addition, as a result of developments in information technology, businesses can communicate with their channel members and consumers progressively at less expense. This provides a significant competitive advantage to businesses another technological development used in the management of distribution channels is the monitoring of the position of the products with the general positioning service (GPS) technology. Through the satellite frameworks, the area of all vehicles can be followed and the organizations and customers can be all the while educated about the accurate area of their items.

Technological developments do not only improve inventory management but also reduce the number of channel members between producers and consumers. Nowadays, consumers are able to order their products from the web or mobile application of businesses. This situation allows businesses to work with less intermediaries and employees.

Promotion:

Promotion is the last element of marketing mix. Since it depends on communication with consumers so as to induce them to purchase more, the developments in information and communication technologies have reshaped promotion activities. Another component that recognizes traditional media from the internet and mobile technologies is that push-type strategies are applied in the traditional advertisement, while pull-type strategies are applied in the internet and mobile advertisements (Li, and Du, 2012). In push-type advertising strategies, businesses transmit their marketing messages legitimately to customers, while in pull-type strategies, businesses have to take permission from consumers in order to send advertising messages (Chen, and Hsieh, 2012).

Beside to advertising, other elements of promotions such as sales promotions and public relations adopt new technologies. Businesses either send coupon as a message or offer coupons via web-based networking media stages. Contrasted with conventional coupons, coupons delivered to consumers via social media and mobile devices are said to be more readable and used. However, businesses should move to Marketing 4.0 in order to survive in the digital era. Marketing 4.0 depends on the management of big data; therefore, businesses should investing in talent management in order to train and/or hire employees who make advanced analysis by using big data. Moreover, technology continues to improve rapidly. Thus, fast movement is the most important business asset now. Businesses should speed up their marketing activities and follow the changes continuously in order to thrive. In order to enhance our understanding of these issues, there is a still need for intensive empirical research which can be the focus of further research.

Conclusion:

This paper has endeavored to uncover the transformative impact of innovation in advertising exercises. Marketing activities have first emerged after the industrial revolution and as technology has developed, marketing has converted into Marketing 2.0, Marketing 3.0 and Marketing 4.0 respectively, aligns with the changes in industries, markets, and costumes.

It is called attention to that the center focuses, fundamental destinations, and usage of each showcasing ideas are unique in relation to each other. Particularly, information and communication technologies have induced a substantial change in both marketing concepts and marketing mix elements. Digital technology is one of the main drivers of world economic development.

Almost all countries are competing to observe digital transformation quickly. It does not mean that industry 4.0 is without challenges. The increasing unemployment rate caused by the reduction in human services, increasing factory waste, and decreasing socialization are among the particular concerns of the community. This change brings us to the fourth wave industrial revolution or Industry 4.0, which is the latest trend in the world of such sophisticated technology. It is inevitable where technological changes reach all the activities of human life to make everything more effective and efficient in a relatively short period.

The digital age begins to change where people are no longer interested in consuming bulk goods and services. The information about prices and testimonials from previous customers are readily available. Digitalization happens to all aspects, including business organizations, business processes, and communication devices.

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